

Reshaping voice

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Transforming a voice file into an image has revealed detail never before seen through any other operation. The MATLAB/OCTAVE command `'reshape'` using parameters matching the speaker's pitch frequency brought out unusual features inherited from vocal chord movements during voicing.

The image below shows a spectrogram (top tier) of utterance `'an oily rag'` by female speaker `'aks'` from the TIMIT database; the middle tier shows the pitch trajectory from a `'reshape'` at 226 Hz, while the bottom tier has the same path reshaped for 233 Hz.

The high dynamics of pitch motion during this utterance cannot be contained in one image for very long, a kind of `'aliasing'`; a few Hz more in the `'reshape'` command was enough to alter the display.

It is not obvious from spectral methods that vocal chords may actually behave independently, contributing different trajectory features to the passing pressure wave; Fourier Transforms are simply not fine enough - time/frequency limitations - and just blend them.

To follow each chord's vibration, appended copies of the pitch tiers and erasure of duplicate traces, yielded the images shown further below. The first image has the `'226 Hz'` contiguous reshape, while the second has the `'233 Hz'`. The utterance content `'an oily rag'` is spelled out above each image to correlate somewhat - though far from exactly - trajectory structures with voicing. Notice

1. The two chords show independent dynamics, particularly during utterance of vowels
2. Amusingly, both chords show mouthlike `'openings'` during utterance of `'OI'`
2. A torsion feature is evident during the `'L'` sound, perhaps a result of `'feedback'`
3. Trajectory splitting is only present in the `'top'` chord during the open-mouth `'A'` sound

A N O I L Y R A G

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One more example; female speaker 'elc', utterance 'wash water all year', same TIMIT database.

The top panel has a spectrogram, while the lower panels have reshapes at 204 Hz, 193 Hz, 183 Hz, and 175 Hz respectively; scanning down to tiers free of 'aliasing' shows continuously voiced features, albeit crudely correlated with content.

All these acoustical renderings likely display some vocal tract structures beyond just chord vibrations.